

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B430
 Date: 18 Feb 2009
 Take Off: 11:07:08
 Landing: 16:39:29
 Flight Time: 5h 32m 21s

Campaign: APPRAISE CLOUDS Flight
Operating Area: Over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. Area Alpha.

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Al Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	Manchester University	
5	Flight Manager	Stephen Devereau	FAAM	
6	Core Chem1	Ruth Purvis	FAAM	
7	Core Chem2	Stephane Bauguitte	FAAM	
8	Cloud Physics 1	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
9	Cloud Physics 2	Jim Crawford	FAAM	
10	Mission Scientist 2	Dave Kindred	Met Office	
11	Mission Scientist 3	Zhiqiang Cui	Leeds University	
12	CVI	Paul Barratt	Met Office	
13	Wet Nephelometer	Martin Glew	Met Office	
14	AMS	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University	
15	Manchester Cloud	James Dorsey	Manchester University	
16				
17				
18				

The following log sheets are not available for this flight :

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Track plot	No plot available
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	No In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
CVI	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
Manchester Cloud	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	30 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090218_r0_b430_120153_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090218_r0_b430_130153_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090218_r0_b430_140153_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090218_r0_b430_150153_1hz.avi
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faam-video-ufc_faam_20090217_r0_b430_125205_1hz.avi
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FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B430

Date: APPRAISE CLOUDS Flight

Project: 18 Feb 2009

Location: Over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. Area Alpha.

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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094351		!	-.03 kft	308	Horace restarted after freeze
105448		!	-.04 kft	128	engine start
110733		T/O	0.38 kft	211	from Cranfield 110708
110909		!	3.0 kft	035	CPC logging started
111504		!	10.0 kft	253	Nev JW zero
111600		!	10.0 kft	253	started WAS sampling sequence
112813		!	6.0 kft	171	JW Nev zero?
113346		!	4.3 kft	138	approach to Bosc start 112420
114037		!	0.70 kft	230	start final approach B Down 113840
114144		!	0.12 kft	229	end approach BD at 50ft
114251	114354	Profile 1.1	1.5 - 2.3 kft	233	from 50ft -5s
114809	115659	Profile 2.1	2.3 - 13.0 kft	250	
115132		!	6.1 kft	250	JW Nev zero
115435		!	10.0 kft	092	Nev JW zero
115700	121227	Run 1.1	13.0 - 12.7 kft	054	
115815		!	13.0 kft	071	Nev JW zero
120730		!	13.0 kft	062	overhead Chilbolton
120849		!	13.0 kft	059	Nev JW zero
121352	122512	Run 2.1	11.0 kft	257	
122405		!	11.0 kft	253	in icing, turb probe so far ok
122526	122617	Profile 3.1	10.9 - 10.1 kft	224	
122658	124435	Run 3.1	10.0 kft	040	at end profile
123629		!	10.0 kft	078	JW Nev zero
124005		!	10.0 kft	061	overhead Chilbolton
124435	124555	Profile 4.1	10.0 - 9.0 kft	257	
124457		!	9.8 kft	251	oh Chil
124555	125813	Run 4.1	9.0 kft	256	
125814	130003	Profile 5.1	9.0 - 8.0 kft	253	
130004	131855	Run 5.1	8.0 kft	047	
130952		!	8.0 kft	072	Nev JW zero
131352		!	8.0 kft	071	o/h Chil
131856	132022	Profile 6.1	8.0 - 7.1 kft	247	
132023	133257	Run 6.1	7.1 - 7.0 kft	259	
133257	133426	Profile 7.1	7.0 - 6.1 kft	256	
133427	135402	Run 7.1	6.0 kft	073	
134038		!	6.0 kft	072	JW Nev zero
134243		!	6.0 kft	072	Heimann Cal
134920		!	6.0 kft	059	o/h Chil
135402	135532	Profile 8.1	6.0 - 5.0 kft	259	
135427		!	5.8 kft	250	oh Chil
135533	141210	Run 8.1	5.0 kft	259	
140729		!	5.0 kft	254	JW Nev zero
141211	141433	Profile 9.1	5.0 - 3.5 kft	055	
141433	142723	Run 9.1	3.5 kft	071	
142545		!	3.5 kft	019	oh Chil
142724	142915	Profile 10.1	3.5 - 2.1 kft	106	
142916	144945	Run 10.1	2.1 kft	256	
142958		!	2.1 kft	256	oh Chil at start run 10.1
144945	145903	Profile 11.1	2.1 - 12.7 kft	175	
145436		!	8.1 kft	053	Nev JW zero
145528		!	8.9 kft	303	Heimann cal
145904	150139	Profile 11.2	12.7 - 10.6 kft	243	
150139	151825	Run 11.1	10.6 - 10.5 kft	058	
150731		!	10.5 kft	074	Nev JW zero
151416		!	10.5 kft	073	o/h Chil
151826	151857	Profile 12.1	10.5 - 11.0 kft	285	chil
151913	153103	Run 12.1	11.0 - 10.7 kft	262	
153044		!	11.0 kft	255	Nev JW zero

153134	153238	Profile 13.1	10.3 - 9.6 kft	166 start at end run
153239	154819	Run 13.1	9.6 - 9.5 kft	044
153321		!	9.5 kft	045 Nev JW zero
154206		!	9.5 kft	075 Nev JW zero
154424		!	9.5 kft	075 oh Chil
154819	155350	Profile 14.1	9.5 - 5.0 kft	281 oh chil 154855
155351	155554	Run 14.1	5.0 - 4.9 kft	256 oh chil 154855
155554	155727	Profile 15.1	4.9 - 4.0 kft	255
155728	160039	Run 15.1	4.0 kft	253
155812		!	4.0 kft	253 NJW zero
160049	160234	Profile 16.1	4.2 - 6.0 kft	241
160234	161303	Run 16.1	6.0 - 6.1 kft	042
160350		!	6.0 kft	062 NJW zero
161348		!	6.8 kft	072 OHC
161416	161711	Profile 17.1	7.3 - 10.0 kft	064 started end run
162928		!	4.2 kft	041 BBR extend, Heimann off
164019		Land	0.02 kft	357 163929

Sortie Brief: APPRAISE-Clouds: mixed-phase cloud studies

Date: 18 Feb 2009

B430: t/o 10:30z

M.Sci: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes in frontal clouds in association with the Chilbolton radar facility.

Sortie Location: Over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. Area Alpha.

Sortie Summary: Perform a series of runs at a series of altitudes below cloud base (if possible), within and above the cloud, along the azimuth that is being scanned by the radar. Information on the run orientation and altitude to be flown will be provided by scientists at Chilbolton using VHF radio (call-sign "Radsearch"). Where the radar identifies a small-scale feature of interest, the aircraft may abort a long leg in order to turn to re-penetrate it. Where either the aircraft or radar identifies a particular horizontal layer of interest, the aircraft may fly a sawtooth pattern so as to provide a sequence of profiles through it. It is desired that the aircraft flight legs start/finish in the Chilbolton overhead. This benefits the validation of vertically-pointing radar/lidar retrievals of supercooled cloud layers. This requires turns to be done within controlled airspace and so may limit the number of occasions that this is possible.

Sortie Detail :

- a) Take off & climb to FL100 to transit to operating area at Chilbolton.
- b) When at suitable location descend from transit altitude to 1000ft agl, or to lowest altitude allowed by operating restrictions. Fly 10min **clear air** leg in vicinity of Chilbolton.
- c) Perform a profile ascent at 1000ft/min along the azimuth and through the cloud system up to FL330 or to above cloud top, whichever is lower.
- d) Fly a series of 40-60km level flight legs along the azimuth scanned by the radar at altitudes defined by the radar or as determined from previous profile. Ideally, just above cloud base, throughout the cloud, just below and just above cloud top. Duration of each leg ~10 minutes. Legs should extend over Chilbolton. During incloud legs AMS should sample off CVI inlet unless tip iced up (but sample off Rosemount inlet out of cloud). Filters to be exposed on out of cloud legs only.
- e) Where the radar identifies a feature of interest or one that is penetrated by the aircraft along any leg, the leg may be interrupted to fly one or more butterfly patterns. Each butterfly consists of a minimum of two minutes straight/level that includes penetration of the feature followed by turns that allow re-penetration of the feature during the reciprocal part of the pattern.
- f) Where a defined layer of interest (such as a shallow layer of supercooled liquid water) is identified by the aircraft or radar, the long leg may be flown as a sawtooth leg with ascents/descents at 1000ft/min, extending 1000ft above and below the layer level (M.Sci may request level segments of 1 minute).
- g) Repeat items d) to e) as long as flight endurance or cloud conditions permit.
- h) End with below-cloud clear air aerosol leg (10 min) if possible, before recovering to destination airfield.

PROJECT BRIEF: APPRAISE-Clouds – mixed-phase cloud studies

Scientific Aims: The purpose of this project is to obtain detailed microphysical measurements in stratiform cloud systems, altocumulus clouds, wave clouds and cumulus clouds within the temperature regime in which ice particles will likely co-exist with liquid (typically 0 to -30C).

The flight plans are designed to characterise the aerosol above and below the cloud and infer aerosol fluxes into the cloud layer by combination with the vertical wind measurements and the microphysical characteristics within the cloud layer.

Constant altitude flight legs of approximately 50 km (10 minutes flying) will be made:

- In the boundary layer to measure the aerosol size distributions (from 10 nm to 100 μm), CCN, aerosol composition from 30 nm to 1 μm using the ToF AMS; larger particles and non-volatile material such as refractory material will be measured using EDAX analysis of filter samples.
- Near cloud base within cloud to measure the cloud droplets that have been activated from CCN, interstitial particles and larger particles that have fallen from cloud top. In addition the onset of ice will be observed using the CPI, CAPS and 2-D probes in cloud.
- Middle of the cloud passes will be made at temperatures where key processes will be expected to be initiated (-6C to -9C) for the Hallett-Mossop process or around -15C where fragmentation of dendritic crystals may be important.
- Near cloud top and within the cloud to measure entrainment and aerosols within entrained eddies and ice particles within the cloud; in colder clouds ice initiation will occur in this region.
- Above the cloud to measure the properties of aerosol particles that can potentially be entrained into the clouds.

In-situ measurements from the aircraft are performed in close coordination with the CAMRa radar and lidar facilities at Chilbolton, Hants.

Weather conditions: Stratiform, or altocumulus clouds lying over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. This may or may not be generating precipitation at the surface. It is particularly desirable if the mean wind direction lies between about 220 and 280 degrees. This allows the aircraft to fly legs along the radar beam whilst staying closely parallel to the mean wind direction.

Key instruments and their operation.

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer, CR2
- GPS, GIN, turbulence probe – When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud/Aerosol Physics/Chemistry

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, CDP. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops (>100micron) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- 2DS, CAPS and FSSP – as above
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where a run is only partially in cloud and is starting in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Manager's log.
- TWC. If possible, a profile in clear air is desirable for calibration purposes.
- AMS, SMPS/WCPC (- to sample off both Rosemount and CVI inlets)
- Filters

CVI inlet sampling: residuals (and $\text{Ly}\alpha$) incloud; aerosols out of cloud (PCASP, CPC)

Mission Scientist Debrief: APPRAISE-Clouds: mixed-phase cloud studies:
Flight Number: B430, 18th Feb 2009 (Take-off 11:07z, landed 16:39z)
Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims & operating area: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes in frontal and other clouds in association with the Chilbolton radar facility.

Weather conditions: In the days leading up to Feb 18th, the synoptic situation was dominated by a region of high pressure centred out in the SW approaches (extending over to NW France), by another region of high pressure over Scandinavia, and a number of low pressure systems lying out to the west in the mid N Atlantic and to the NW over Iceland and out further west towards Greenland. Further areas of low pressure were positioned over the Black Sea and N-NE Europe. The net effect of this was that the southern UK and Ireland were dominated and protected by the effect of the high pressure out to the SW. This caused frontal systems advecting in from the west to be deflected around to the north of the UK over Scotland and back around into the North Sea, skirting with the eastern coastline of the UK. By midnight on the 18th, one such front lay almost along the 0° longitude line over eastern England, the northern portion (to the east of northern England/Scotland) moving further to the east as a warm front and the southern section (over the midlands and SW England) returning west over the southern UK as a cold front, but moving only slowly west because of the presence of the slowly retreating high pressure area. Associated with this front, forecasts suggested a degree of low and mid level cloud would also advect west over southern England during the day. The exact positioning and western extent of this cloud cover varied a little between models, ECMWF suggesting the front would progress further to the west (over Wales and Cornwall) than the MetOffice forecasts (eg compare cloud forecasts from the MetOffice mesoscale model and ECMWF models for midday, Figures 1 and 2). Based on this information a 10:30z take-off was planned to catch the cloud forecasted to be present over the Chilbolton area by midday and early afternoon.

Figures 1 and 2: Cloud forecasts for midday from MetOffice mesoscale model (Fig 1 - left) and ECMWF (Fig 2, right) from the midnight run of each model

Figure 3 below shows the actual synoptic chart for midday on the 18th, where the front over southern England is marked as a stationary entity running N-S through the midlands and southern England (positioned just the west of the Isle of Wight and directly across the 255 radial from Chilbolton – the normal heading for aircraft runs out to the west).

Figure 3: Synoptic chart for 12:00z February 18th 2009

Figure 4 below shows the cloud reflectivity time series for the upward pointing 35GHz radar at Chilbolton. It can be seen that there is a fairly stable layer of low-midlevel cloud present at 09:00z, so it was decided to remain close to the proposed take-off time but slip it by 30 mins to 11:00z for convenience.

Figure 4: Radar reflectivity for 35GHz cloud radar at Chilbolton

Summary of the flight: Following take-off at Cranfield, locally the low level cloud cover extended between 750 and 4900ft. There were some higher clouds above this, and when the transit altitude of FL100 was achieved the CPI was seeing pristine dendritic crystals as the transit started out just in the base of the midlevel cloud layer (692mbar, -9.92°C). During the transit west, some holes in the cloud top (CT) were visible just to the south, however, the cloud remained mixed phase (including dendrites). Following a turn to the south at the end of the transit leg and the start of the descent into the Chilbolton/Boscombe Down region the aircraft dropped out of the mid level cloud at FL75 (765mar, -3.56°C). At this time reports from the radar at Chilbolton indicated mid-level CT at 3.6km (11.8kft), bases at 2.5km (8.2kft) with a layer of stratocumulus below. In the profile descent the Sc CT was seen at 2100ft (on a 1013mb setting) but the layer was only ~200ft thick. A missed approach was carried out at Boscombe Down airfield, followed by a profile ascent P1 up to 2300ft, for the start of a short aerosol SLR leg (R0) west. AMS reported seeing a pollution signal in the Boscombe approach, while core chemistry reported two peaks in NO_x of 25 and 20ppb respectively. An update from Chilbolton reported an ice cloud layer overhead at 3.8km (12.5kft) falling at least by 1.2km (4kft) and seeding a Sc layer below at 1.5km (5kft). CT temperature was reported at -12°C with a strong inversion producing a capping layer. Reflectivity was +5dbz in places hence there was almost certainly supercooled water at CT.

The aerosol SLR leg R0 (931mbar, 4.76°C) was terminated and profile P2 started still heading west. CT was encountered at 4.2kft (868mbar, 2.08°C). CPI reported seeing precipitation (ppt), which initially was large drops but then became all ice. P2 was continued during the turn at the SW end of the radial, after which CT was encountered at FL112 (662mbar, -12.4°C). P2 was terminated at FL130 (619mbar, -8.9°C), and SLR R1.1 carried out inbound to CH at that level (above CT). Chilbolton reported a consistent cloud layer out to 60km range, with a region of stronger reflectivity at 15-20km range (west of CH). After passing over Chilbolton at FL130 (-9.75°C) and turning, a fast descent was carried out to get into the cloud layer for the outbound run. Chilbolton reported showers at 18-22km range. CT was encountered at FL120 (644mb, -13.32°C), and R2.1 started (at about 15-20km out from CH) in-cloud at FL110 (668mbar, -11.4°C).

This pattern of reciprocal runs outbound from, and inbound to Chilbolton was then undertaken at decreasing altitude steps (of generally 1000ft intervals) through the cloud layers. The profile descents were carried out just after passing CH outbound and just prior to the turn at the SW end of the radial. Table 1 summarises details of these runs/profiles.

Essentially, there was significant structure observed across the SLR runs in the horizontal, with an embedded convective feature persisting within the 15-30km range from CH throughout the period of the flight. In the absence of any wind, the pattern remained fairly fixed. Earlier on (ie at higher levels in the mid level cloud) the variation manifested as changes in the degree of glaciation across a run (from being essentially wholly liquid in certain regions to being mixed phase or glaciated in others). In addition there were cloud free zones particularly at the mid-leg distance (40-60km). Later, there seemed to be little cloud at lower levels beyond the “feature” to the SW except near the turn.

Table 1:

P # (d) Run #	in/out bound (I/O)	Flight level	Run Pressure (mbar)	Temp start/end SLR(°C)	Comments/observations
P2.1 R1.1	I	FL130	619	-8.90 -9.53	During P2.1 CT was seen at FL112/662mb and -12.4°C so R1.1 was above inversion. 3GHz radar report showers at 18-22km range. NB see higher T above inversion
Fast descent R2.1	O	FL110	668	-11.40 -11.81	During Descent CT at FL120/644mb, -13.32°C. R2.1 starts~20km out from CH. Core Cloud sees ice, CPI mixed phase – predom. Horizontal variability, with gap in cloud at 2/3 distance. Later sections ~all liquid.
P3.1 R3.1	I	FL100	695	-9.24 -9.16	Descent outbound, continues in turn. Lots of horizontal structure, CPI initially all water, then ice. CPI sees pristine plates and dendrites then out of cloud between 2/3 and 1/3 range. PPI scan from CH sees patch high Zdr poss planar crystals 18-22km out, and seeding of low level cloud. On entering “feature” CPI sees mixed phase precip, but not too many drops. After passing CH, CPI saw small needles/ dendrites.
P4.1 R4.1	O	FL90	722	-6.94 -6.59	Over CH – mixed phase, precip, then bumpy in the “feature”, CPI saw concs small drops, many small irregulars. CAPS pitot tube iced up. Out of cloud after feature for some time. Approaching SW end of run, CPI sees large columns, dendrites + extremely small pellets. CVI picked up a lot of liquid water and an increase in particle number
P5.1 R5.1	I	FL80	750	-4.56 -4.15	P5.1 in SW turn, out of cloud, but precip from above. Latest 12z vis satellite picture suggests thicker cloud SW end of run, evidence of embedded convection at 20km W, where feature sampled, no bright band so precip is ice then? No precip 45km out. Bumpy in centre of feature – pristine columns and SC water. Small increase in CO (10ppb) too + dry Neph response. No cloud or precip over CH. In turn CIP100 sees dendrites, 2DS pristine snow too. Zdr signature at 20-30km, streaks to 2.2km
P6.1 R6.1	O	FL70	780	-2.78 -2.19	R6.1 starts just into cloud & feature. CPI sees needles + SC water. No elevation in Chem this time. Then out of cloud – still bumpy. Small isolated layer cloud at 45km then no cloud, no precip. MSci3 – still evidence of convective activity small area/strips N-S west of CH
P7.1	I	FL60	810	-0.31	No cloud in SW turn, the into cloud (200-

R7.1				-1.09	300m below CT) at 80-90km west, only water. Radar scan sees single band 20km out, poss rain to surface. At feature, cloud is N and S of 146 (which is in gap), but CPI sees large ice, then water.
P8.1 R8.1	O	FL50	841	+1.33 +1.55	3GHz radar sees band at 20km, large echoes from 4km tops, maybe liquid in updraughts, ice falling down sides? Neph and core chem sees structure, but 146 into CTs 40km out – no effect from precip. CH RHIs suggest 20km feature diminished. Ice at upper level falling down to low levels
P9.1 R9.1	I	FL35	890	2.52 2.25	P9.1 and R9.1 after SW turn due to ATC. CPI reports lots liquid water in “feature” (eyeball estimate 1g/m ³). CH reports 20km feature dissipating, growing at 15km double layer, 2-4km and another below with CT at 2km – reports significant virga from upper into lower level
P10.1 R10.1	O	2300ft	937	4.05 4.14	RHI scans show feature 15km dissipating, possible plume now collapsing. Core cloud reports precip increased x3 from start of run. RHI sees new growing feature at 18km, upper layer 2-4km above another with CT at 2km

The details of variation in the feature just to the west of CH, are best illustrated by the series of RHI scans made by the 3GHz cloud radar at Chilbolton along the 255° (received onboard the aircraft during the flight). These are shown in Figure 5 (a-f).

After completing this series of descending runs and profiles, a profile ascent P11.1 was undertaken to get up to the 4km (13kft) CT region of the mid layer clouds highlighted by the RHI scans. In order to carry out a continuous profile it was started in the SW turn, continued for 25km inbound to CH and was then completed during and after a turn to head back to the SW. At 4.9kft (845mbar, 1.59°C just after SW turn), the aircraft was out of CT by some way. A CT was encountered at FL111 (667mbar, -12.11) heading back W to the SW end of the radial. Being above cloud and the inversion, P11.1 was terminated at FL125 (631mbar, -7.93°C), and P11.2 started to head back down to the cloud layer. P11.2 was completed just after the SW turn, and R11.1 started at FL105 (681mbar, -10.89°C) inbound just in CT. A series of SLR runs inbound to and outbound from CH were now undertaken primarily to investigate this upper mid-level cloud region. These SLRs are summarised in Table 2 below. The mission concluded by carrying out a run inbound in the lower part of the cloud at around the 0°C level, to position for the RTB. The aircraft landed at 16:39z at Cranfield.

Table 2:

P # (d) Run #	in/out bound (I/O)	Flight level	Run Pressure (mbar)	Temp start/end SLR(°C)	Comments/observations
P11.2 R11.1	I	FL105	681	-10.89 -10.65	R11.1 started ~in CT. Cloud layer is thin. CPI sees Hex plates (falling from above?). Soon run is just below CB. Within 10km of CH, aircraft anti-icing alarm triggered. Radar reported updraught + liquid at 25km range, high Zdr – ice spilling out between 10.5-8.5kft
P12.1 R12.1	O	FL110	670	-11.69 N/A	CPI sees liquid cloud – occasional ice & pylons/probes starting to ice up. In-out of holes in CT, can see sun disc at times. Radar reports high Zdr 18-25km range, with virga. Much higher reflectivity than previously. Run ends just above CT
P13.1 R13.1	I	FL95	708	-8.47 -8.49	Descent (in SW turn) to just below CT to measure precip/virga. Into thin cloud at 40km, and thick cloud at 25-30km. Fairly cloud free over CH, CPI & core cloud seeing snow in turn.
P14.1 R14.1	O	FL50	841	0.96 1.69	Descent started ~ over CH. R14.1 started about 45km out, just into cloud initially, then at or above CT. Run cut short
P15.1 R15.1	O	FL40	873	2.92	Brief descent to get into cloud –outbound. R15.1 starts at about 65km range. Only in cloud at SW end of run from ~75km
P16.1 R16.1	I	FL60	812	0.10 -0.61	P16.1 before and during SW turn. ATC prevent higher run to examine 10dbz feature. Cloud particles mostly liquid, some ill formed aggregates

Figure 6 shows the full time series of reflectivity from the 35GHz vertical point radar at Chilbolton for Feb 18th. This shows how stable the mid cloud layer was throughout the flight. This is because there was close to zero horizontal wind at all times, when the front became stationary over the area (Figure 8 – UK synoptic cart at 13:00z) . This accounts for the persistence of the embedded convection between 15 and 30km range from Chilbolton throughout the flight (Figure7 – high resolution visible satellite picture 13:00z).

Figure 5(a-f): RHI scans from the 3GHz cloud radar at Chilbolton at 13:02, 13:54, 14:35, 15:24, 5:40z and 15:57 respectively, showing the persistence of embedded convective cloud features at 10-30km range from Chilbolton on Feb 18th 2009. The convection was capped at ~4km by a strong inversion layer.

Figures 6 : Time series of Radar reflectivity factor for the 35GHz vertically pointing cloud radar at Chilbolton for Feb 18th .

Figure7 (left) & 8 (right): High resolution visible satellite image from 1300z (fig 7) and corresponding synoptic chart (fig 8) showing the position of the embedded convection and the stationary front just to west of Chilbolton respectively.

Notes on instrumentation:

Pitot tubes on CIP instruments suffered icing at times. The 3010 CPC on the CVI was not working. Dry nephelometer display on Horace was meaningless. 2DS did not survive power change over prior to take-off.

Mission Scientist's Log [APPRMSE - Clouds]

Flight No B...430 Date ...18/02/09... Name ...K.N. BOWER... Page ...1... of ...14.

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					(230/2kts).
10:55:50	ICNB				Engine Start 4-1
10:58:32	ICNB				Power Change Over
					(210/3kts)
11:00:08	"				Taxi (1027/330ft)
					(170/2kts)
11:07:28	"				Rolling
11:07:53	"				Take off
		760ft			Low level cloud - CB. - dark/gloomy.
11:11:10	"	4900ft			CT. - Some Mid level clouds - above - thin
11:14:46	arrived transit level	FL100	253	52°15'/0°30'	- CPI seeing positive dendrites
11:15:40	≡ 11:16:20	ICNB	(@+48s)		Time Check. - just in base of the mid level cloud.
11:16:50	Trans	FL100	253	52°12'/0°42'	696mb, -9.92°/-9.93° 5mb/340°
11:17:30	Trans	FL100	252	52°12'/0°48'	696mb, -9.56°C/-12.97° 3mb/291°
					Mobs in CT. here. to LHS.
					Still mixed plus clouds - inc dendrites
11:24:34	PO ↓	9.7kft	188	52°0'/1°30'	Start descent 702mb -9.42°/-9.95°C, 0m/s
11:25:40	PO	7.5kft	184	51°54'/1°30'	Turning - out of mid level cloud 765mb -3.56°/-7.35°C
11:26:56	PO Int	FL60	179	51°48'/1°30'	810mb, 0.51°/-2.95°C, 5m/s/55°
					(QFE 1013 Boscombe)
		11800ft	←		IRC - M3 CT 3.6 km -12°C
		8200ft			CB 2.5km
					Sc layer underneath.
					c. mphys upper layer - needs looking at
11:29:50	PO Rezone	FL60	175	51°36'/1°30'	812mb 0.66°C/-1.45°C 5m/s/46°

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.....430 Date ...18/02/09 Name K.N. BOWEN Page ...2 of ...14.

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					AMS - reports
11.36.30	2 P0	2100ft			CT (on 1013 RFE).
11.37.04	P0	2000	235	51°12'/1°30'	942mb 5.28°/5.55°C 0mbs - local CB.
11.37.25	P0	1.9kt	236	51°12'/1°30'	CB. 942mb. 5.31°/5.57° 1mbs/183°
					Variable
	P0	1.66kt.			Clear Air
11.39.32	P0	1500	230	51°12'/1°36'	959mb 5.22°/4.98°C 4mbs/150°
11.40.14	P0	1000	227	51°6'/1°36'	973mb 6.5°/5.06°C 4mbs/158°
11.40.52	P0	500	231	51°6'/1°42'	994mb 6.36°/7.24°C 3mbs/151°
11.41.30	P0 and P1	0.0kt	230	51°6'/1°42'	50ft/1011mb 7.57°/7.87°C 2mbs/151°
11.42.19	P1.1	1000	230	51°6'/1°42'	977mb 6.45°/7.15°C 4mbs/160°
11.42.37	P1.1	1500	233	51°6'/1°48'	959mb 5.95°/6.73°C 3mbs/165°
11.43.06	P1.1	2000	233	51°6'/1°48'	941mb 5.09°/6.04°C 2mbs/157°
11.43.47	P1.1/P0	2300	244	51°0'/1°48'	OH CH condition 931mb 4.45°/5.72°
					(12500 ft ← falling - 4000 ft ← or 5000 ft) thin layer ice cloud 3500m falling at least 1200m seeding SE below alt 1500m. st
					CT w -12°C
					strong inv - capping layer
					Reflectivity w + Solbg in places →
					reasonable LWC
					Almost certainly SCold W20 at top
					→ ending cloud overturning at top
11.48.08	P0 and P2.1	2.3kt	250	51°0'/2°12'	931mb 4.76°/5.84°C 3mbs/193°
11.49.50	P2.1	4.2kt	251	50°54'/2°24'	CT 868mb 2.08°/2.91° 2mbs/248°

CPI "part along - large drops - new ice"

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.430 Date 18/02/09 Name K.N. BOWEN Page 3 of 14

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					IRC - Paul Williams - low cloud pres? No.
					CH - along 235°
					consistent layer ~ 60km
					stronger reflectivity 15-20km range
11.53.14	P2.1	8.3kft	250	50°48'/2°42'	turning 742mb -5.37°/-5.58°C 2m/s/153°
11.55.32	P2.1	11.2kft	48	50°48'/2°36'	CT. 662mb -12.4°/-11.5°C 2m/s/352°
11.56.57	P2.1 and R1.	12.9kft	54	50°54'/2°30'	619mb / FL130 -8.9°/-40.8°C 10m/s/349°
					CVI OK as inlet.... but
					CPC - problems - not same as any other CPCs
					PCASP OK
					MS03 - Radar Reflectivity
					- low level - general thickening since ↑ low intermediate levels
					MS03 - IRC - looks like small shower.
					18-22 km out from Utara at (14)
					CPI -
12.07.16	R1.1	FL130	71	51°6'/1°24'	On CH & turning 618mb -9.75°/-32.57° 7m/s/11°
					MS03: 36Hz Radar - Shower - alt ~ 22km
12.12.14	R1.1 end	12.9kft	254	51°6'/1°24'	Descending gradually to cloud 619mb -9.53°/-31.89°
12.12.54	Descent	12.0kft	260	51°6'/1°30'	CT 644mb -13.32°/-22.13 4m/s/301°
12.13.49	R2.1 start	FL110	256	51°6'/1°30'	Coc Cloud - Ice. 665mb -11.4°/-12.14 4/302°
					CPI - mixed phase - predom liquid H ₂ O
					some larger ice Xalts too.
12.15.45	R2.1	FL110	256	51°0'/1°40'	Through CB here. -11.22°/-9.95°C 669mb 2/350°

[SW]

[CN]

preferred - PL's [Odds - inboard]
Eens - outboard]

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... 430 Date ... 18/02/09 Name ... K.N. BOWER Page ... 4 ... of ... 14

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
11.35 ish					AMS - reports of pollution in Boreas approach - RUTH - 11.40 ish - also saw signals
12.19.39	R2.1	F110	255	51°0'/2°12'	Well into dead now. 669mb -11.85/-9.97°C 1/319° CPI - almost all liquid now
					Core Chem - 2 peaks on approach to BD. NO _x - 35 ppb NO ₂ - 20 ppb
12.25.10	R2.1.01 / R3.1.3	FL110	254	50°48'/2°42'	669mb -11.81/-10.51°C 2mb/199° gently descending to start next run CPI - ...
12.26.17	R3.1.01 / R3.1.3	FL100	125	50°48'/2°48'	695mb, -9.24°/-8.04 2mb/118° turb probe OK. - not used up yet. CPI - lots horizontal structure. start run all LW - now all ice
X					MSi 3 :- TWC - section of Sc - by mid level cloud, ppt to surface Chil - PPI → patch light ppt - from that med RMI → high z dr consistent with cirrus planar xtals ~ 18-22km West & in top 300m of cloud
12.30.36	R3.1	FL100	72	50°54'/2°24'	CPI :- pristine plates / dendrites 696mb -8.81°C/-9.92°C 2mb/6°

SW

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... 430 Date 18/02/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 5 of 14

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
12:32.08	R3.1	FL100	73	50°54'/2°12'	Out of cloud here 696mb -8.86/-9.56°C 2m/s/25° 3GM ₂ Radar:- 20km West - significant echoes either side of feature. CPI - seeing lots small drops (in trigger!!) feature ahead of us now.
12.36.50	R3.1	FL100	78	51°0'/1°42'	Into cloud feature. 695mb -8.89/-7.86°C 2m/s/33° TWC - Cloud Stacks → nr 2-2.5km CH - RMI - streaks high 2dr (20-22km, W) plenty seeding low cloud at ~ 25km (CPI) → mixed phase ppt - not too many drops. MS ₃ - 1-2 small lower level / CPI -
12.40.09	R3.1	FL100	61	51°6'/1°24'	turning OH CH 696 -9.14/-9.32°C 4m/s/20° - report from ground - crystal type? CPI - small needles + dendrites
12.44.15	R3.1	FL100	57	51°6'/1°18'	turning: 696mb -9.24/-9.89°, 4m/s/13°
12.44.33	R3.1/P4.1	FL100	257	51°6'/1°24'	698mb -9.16/-9.5 2m/s/322°
12.45.54	P4.1and/R4.1	FL90	256	51°6'/1°30'	722mb -6.94/-8.44° 0m/s OH mixed phase - ppt - few CT
12.47.18	R4.1	FL90	253	51°0'/1°36'	in feature - bumpy. # -7.14°C/-6.4°C 723. #
12.47.56	R4.1	FL90	254	51°0'/1°42'	Out of cloud now 723mb -6.88/-8.94° 4m/s/271°

* OH CH @ 12:44:48

CPI: small dendr drop conc in bumpy section
* needle on 1/c radar

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... 430 Date 15/02/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 6 of 14

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Pilot ch PIP - read over??
					All else OK. ✓
12.54.17	R4.1	FL90	254	50°54'/2°15'	Out of cloud :- -6.41 / -7.13°, 723mb, 3mly/315° large columns / den + extremes small pellets so still seeing this
				<u>NE</u>	2DS - logging restarted at start of run & #
					OVI picked up but LW - ↑ particle N°
					MSi 3 :- (C) feature 20km out... is it convective - splinters / den etc columns
					- lot of very small irregular - pass from bumpy -
12.58.12	R4.1 end / PS.1.1	FL90	253	50°45'/2°42'	723mb -6.59°C / -6.55°C 1mly/182° - "out of cloud" but lots of ppt from above! CPI - still ppt at end of leg - do again full runs
					MSi - latest sat pic - thicker cloud at W end of run
13.00.02	PS.1 end / RS.1	FL80	50	50°45'/2°42'	750mb -4.56° / -3.99°C 2mly/55° MSi 3 12z Vis high resolution Sat image: - def evidence emb convection at 20 km out - end of run - aligned - rough main cloud edge - great ✓ MSi 3 - TWC no bright band over CH ?? TWC - OK - ppt must be ice then. (so ... small ice + HM out of feather)

SW

G

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.....430 Date 18/02/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 7 of 14

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
13.07.09	RS.1	FL80	71	51°0'/2°6'	CPI no ppt here (4Stkm out) 751 mb, -4.04/-5.08°C 6m/s/4° temp probe OK. - still!
13.11.11	RS.1	FL80	74	51°0'/1°42'	751 mb - centre of feature - bumpy proline columns - SC H ₂ O too -4.48°/-7.45° 2m/s/345° Chem - small updraft in CO in that feature dry neph too.....
13.13.52	RS.1	FL80	71	51°6'/1°24'	OH CH, 751 mb, -4.23/-7.55° 3m/s/40° no ppt or cloud here 3m/s/40° PCASP - 15 cm ⁻³ CCN, CPC = Twe - is it poss - missing snowflakes? P18 - new dendrites - wet snow seen Zdr - signature crystal only 20-30 km West OK Strinks down to ~2200m - ZDS - seemg seen proline snowflakes too.
13.18.53	RS lead / R6.1	FL80	240°	51°6'/1°24'	752mb -4.15°C/-7.83°C 1m/s/180°
13.20.22	R6 lead / R6.1	FL70	259°	51°6'/1°30'	780mb just into feature/cloud 780mb -2.78°/231° CPI - needles + SC H ₂ O Core Chem - no elevation in anything that here.
13.21.42	R6.1	FL70	253	51°0'/1°42'	Out of cloud - still bumpy. 761mb -2.19/-5.84°

[CN]

[CN]

on (task 'EA 4pm)

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.....⁴³⁰ Date18/02/09..... NameK N BOWER..... Page 8..... of14.....

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					needles / water on 2Ds / CPI / CP - feature
13.24.42	R6.1	FL70	255	51°0' / 2°0'	small isolated lwr cloud - then nothing - 761 mb, -2.66° / -2.76°, 3 m/s / 272° even less going on here: ppt-wise
					MS: 3 - small areas / strips: N-S - some evidence of convective activity
13.32.56	R6.1 end P7.1	FL70	256	50°48' / 2°42'	761 mb, -2.19° / -3.18°C, 1 m/s / 205°
13.34.26	P7.1 end R7.1	FL60	80	50°48' / 2°42'	810 mb -0.31 / -0.96 3 m/s / 33° (turn and descent under a cloud base - CPI saw nothing 200-300 below C)
13.37.13	R7.1.1	FL60	75	50°54' / 2°30'	Into a band of cloud (30-90 km W of CH) CPI - 0.25 g/m ³ - just water -1.09 / 0.2°C -0.5 / 2.0°C 811 mb + tiny bit ice prod after bank
13.38.36	R7.1	FL60	71	50°54' / 2°24'	Out of cloud - warmer by 1°C too. 811 mb, -0.15° / 2.01°C, 2 m/s / 22° Twe - Red ppt - localized over drill hole. Radar - Scans wind - single band 20km bank bank mid level band - stable. rain rate slow likely -
13.46.15	R7.1	FL60	59	51°0' / 1°42'	Start of "feature" - but main weather is N and S of us - CPI - large ice 811 mb, +0.26 / -5.02°C, 3 / 22° CPI - starting to see water - numerous ice
13.49.14	R7.1	FL60	59		OH CH 811 mb, -1.07 / -0.02 7 m/s / 1°

(0.2-0.25 g/m³ CARS CW)

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.....⁴³⁰ Date^{18/02/09} Name^{K.N. BOWER} Page⁹ of¹⁴

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
13.53.59	DZ.1 / PS.	FL60	261	51°6' / 1°18'	810mb -1.09°C / -0.23°C 4m/s / 346°
[CH] 13.54.23	PS.1 / RS.1	FL50	251	51°6' / 1°24'	0M CH 816mb -0.79°C / 10.07
13.55.32	PS.1 / RS.1	FL50	258	51°6' / 1.97°	841mb 1.33° / -1.97°C 133°C / -1. 4m/s / 296°
					MSci3 3613 -
					2 distinct bands - rear
					20km of 22 km - distance from CH.
					large eddies from 4km tops OK
					Core Chen or distinct deliveries too
					Neph very some structure too
					MSci3 - maybe LWC in updraft?
					diff - ice - glaciating - falling down sides
14.00.48	RS.1	FL50	255	51°0' / 2°0'	just into CTs - ~ 40km alt from CH. 842 mb, 0.48 / 0.7°C 1m/s / 255°
14.03.06	RS.1	FL50	263	51°0' / 2°12'	Traffic - avoiding aclin (ATC)
					- just in terms of deal - no effect from part of ov
					- MSci3 :-
					turn sequence RMI =>
					feature at 20km - diminished significance.
					down 13.00 - 13.20 z
					13.54. less significant.
					ice upper level - falling down -
					interesting at low levels! feature - shun
					- poss do need leg out at 2300' to see
					features.
[SW] 14.09.06	RS.1	FL50	255	50°48' / 2°42'	turn at FL50 - traffic 842mb 1.42 / 1.07°C 6/m/s

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.....⁴³⁰ Date^{18/02/09} Name^{K.N. BOWER} Page¹⁰ of¹⁴

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
14.12.09	R8.1 and / p9.1	FL50	55°	50°54'/2°36'	↓, 842mb, 1.55°/0.74°C 4m/s/13°
14.13.43	P9.1	FL40	79°	50°54'/2°30'	87kmb 2.89°/3.01°C 2m/s/10°
14.14.33	P8.1 and R9.1s	FL35	71°	50°54'/2°24'	A7C 890mb/ 2.52°C/3.69' 1mb/32°
					MSi3 - RMI - 20km hazy out now
					more layers
					lw 2, zdr
					ice falling d l
					Above. CH - Glaciating Sc - but at
					T > 0°C !!!
					feature at 25 km diminishing but at
					15km - growing - starting slope away to
					West up to 4km (from 2km looking at RMI)
					MSi3 - lots LW out of window // in feature
					CPI - eye ball $\frac{1}{2}$ LW // here
					MSi3 - 14.13 RMI
					feature 15km - almost double feature ...
					lower feature up to 2km
					(1.5km)
					almost aligned in vertical.
					- significant Virga - trade 4km into lower
					lower level cloud.
					- now more significant low level feature 0.5km
					at Western edge (50km) - should catch
					it - Strong Echoes - 10-15 dbz reflectance.

look at all the unlocated RMI scans from CHILBULTON to understand this update...

So: Sfc - 4km - 3-10km
 - 15km higher here
 - 15km smaller again

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... L80 Date 18/02/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 11 of 19

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					(1023mb p - Bosambi)* Regard P self (good setting - not too far out)
14.21.31	R9.1	FL35	73	51°0'/1°48'	high LWC - MSc3/CPT
[CH] 14.25.36	R9.1	FL35	41	51°6'/1°24'	OH CH, 891mb, 2.63°/3.5°, 5m/s/338°
14.27.22	R9.1 end P10.1	FL35	99	51°12'/1°24'	890mb 2.25°/3.62° 4m/s/356°
[CH] 14.29.12	P10.1/R9.1	2300ft*	252	51°6'/1°24'	OH CH 937mb 4.05°/5.23° 2m/s/246°
					(14.23 RMI 15km - dissipating - poss plume gone up, collapsing top 1km + blurred later more equal ht on either side - Core Cloud - more (3x) ppt/steady rain small peak in # concn still on CH LWC only
					14.06 High Res Vis Sat Picture available.
					B channel - SE - more convective elements + latest IR. available too - no high level
					RMI - changing (14.35) cold cloud. (as observed) dissipating element at 15km - feature 18km taken over as more significant feature vertical strip up, 60km - (13000ft)
[SW] 14.49.44	R10.1 end/P11.1 st	2300ft*	176	50°48'/2°48'	939mb, 4.14°/5.1° 20kft 2m/s/22° MSc3 - [10 mic + 1hr 1CNB ≡ 4m/s]
→ 14.51.38	P11.1	4.9kft	61	50°48'/2°36'	(on 1013mb) - out of dew top by some way. 845mb, 1.59°/1.55° 4m/s/30°

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.....⁴³⁰ Date^{16/02/09} Name^{K.N. Bower.} Page¹² of¹⁴

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
14.56.31	P11.1	FL100	254	51°0'/2°30'	turned back W. 696mb -9.37°/-10.52°C 2mly/212°
14.57.32	P11.1	11.1kt	251	50°54'/2°36'	CT. as head W. 667mb -12.11/11.57°C 3/205°
[SW] 14.59.56	P11.1/P11.2	FL125	243	50°54'/2°42'	631mb [-7.93°/31.22°C]???. 7mly/326°
15.01.36	P11.2/P11.1	FL105	57	50°46'/2°42'	Inbound - in CT 681mb -10.89°/-13.03°C
					Seeing some hex plates now
					- cloud layer is thin
					- CrI Hex plates from above.
					(just below CB -
15.13.26	R11.1	FL105	73	51°6'/1°30'	A/c anti icing alarm. 682mb -10.52°/9.81°C
[CH] 15.14.15	R11.1	FL105	73	51°6'/1°24'	OH OH 683mb -10.7°/9.75° 4mly/10°
					- donakin - leader scene
					- updraft HLVC - at 25km out
					high zdr
					ice scattering
					high zdr - 10500-8500 ft
[missed CH] 15.18.24	R11.1 low P12.1	FL105	285	51°6'/1°24'	683mb -10.65/-9.52 3mly/305°
15.18.52	P12.1 low R12.1	FL110	262	51°6'/1°24'	Outbound 670mb -11.69°/-9.94°C 3/306°
					-11.69 / 9.94°C
					CrI - liquid cloud see small ice
					liquid cloud see larger ice.
					- nylon probes - stalled wing up
					- liquid
					In/out of holes - sun through above

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B⁴³⁰..... Date ^{18/02/09}..... Name ^{K.N. BOWER}..... Page ¹³ of ¹⁴.....

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					High Zdr is 18-25km range now
					opt is Virga.
					Reflectivity much lower than earlier runs
15.30.43	R2.1 and P13.1	FL110	255	50°54'/2°36'	End run just above CT.
					670mb -10.44/-12.89 4m/s/266°
15.32.36	P13.1E R13.1	FL95	45	50°48'/2°36'	Inband - below cloud layer for rpt/Virga
					705mb -8.47/-8.42° 0m/s
					MSi3 :-
					RHI - more vertical extent - edges
					1.5-2 km - layer shg 14-15km W.
					up to 3 km at times
15.39.23	R13.1	FL95	72	51°0'/1°54'	into thin cloud - more ahead.
					709mb -7.99°C/-7.11°C 4m/s/351°
15.41.54	R13.1	FL95	74	51°0'/1°42'	think cloud breaks - short pass -8.42/-7.71°C
					709mb -8.42/-7.71
					MSi - Wind has been very slack - all z's
					to our advantage.
15.44.23	R13.1	FL95	75	51°6'/1°24'	Oh CH - cloud free - ish now.
					709mb -8.69°/-7.96 709mb 2m/s/45°
15.45.40	R13.1	FL95	53	51°6'/1°18'	RH turn. 709mb -8.4°/-8.9°C
					CPI / Core Cloud - seeing snow!
15.46.14	R13.1/P14.1	FL95	281	51°6'/1°18'	709mb -8.49°C/-8.55° 1m/s/221°
15.46.52	P14.1	9.1kft	271	51°6'/1°24'	719mb -7.43/-6.95 1m/s/208°
					Radar: ice at FL95? Snowing over CH
					Two still here....

[SW] short

→
[CH]

→

→
[CH]

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.....¹³⁰ Date ...16/02/09... Name ...R.N. Bower... Page ...14... of ...14...

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Cloud - Cloud < 0°C Haze a R
					WNW - Cloud +30bg
15.53.50	P14.1ad R14.1	FL50	256	51°0'/1°54'	Into Cloud at start - then at or above CT. 841mb 0.96°/-0.01°C 2mbs/3°
15.55.45	P14.1ad P15.1	FL50	255	51°0'/2°0'	842mb 1.69°/-0.53°C 0mbs. still above CT
15.57.26	P15.1 R15.1	FL40	253	50°54'/2°12'	873mb, 2.92°C/2.14°C 1mbs/144°
16.00.35	R15.1 P16.1	FL40	254	50°54'/2°30'	874mb in cloud now. 2.46°C/3.01
16.01.28	R15.1	FL40	254	50°54'/2°24'	Into cloud - 2.62°C/3.04°
16.02.33	R16.1ad R16.1	FL60	42	50°54'/2°24'	812mb 0.1°C/-1.22°C (penetration 16.01.40) was in CT
					MSei.3 :-
					L along 255° + 10dbz any chance of going up?
					No - ATC - capped at FL60 right now.
					RPT - another plume at 20km up to 3.7km
					- mostly LW + some ill formed aggregates.
16.12.54	R16.1 P17.1	FL60	72	51°6'/1°30'	811mb -0.61°/-0.86°C 7mbs/20°
16.13.38	P17.1	FL65	73	51°6'/1°24'	On CH 785mb -0.5°/-3.97°C 8mbs/34°
16.17.10	P17.1 E	FL100	17	51°15'/1°12'	697mb -9.14°/-10.71 4mbs/330°
					(1025 GNM Crankfield)
		1500			CB
		1000			another CB - main
16.40.19	10NS				landing

(SW) →
→

[CH] ↗

*** Opened channel log for #APPCLOUDS at 18/02/2009 11:25:49

[11:25] *** FAAM_MSci (~vircuser@203.52.191.241) has joined #APPCLOUDS

[11:26] [FAAM_MSci] Hi This is bae146

[11:27] [FAAM_MSci] update from Chilolton is required

[11:29] <TomC> Cloud top 3.6 km temperature at Cloud to -12C

[11:30] [FAAM_MSci] Thanks

[11:30] <TomC> base of upper cloud currently about 2.5km with Sc layer beneath, microphysics of upp layer should be very interesting

[11:34] [FAAM_MSci] Passed the message to Keith

[11:35] <TomC> STFC FAAM can't read your description as posted before aircraft joined

[11:37] <STFC> Latest conditions overhead are thin layer of ice crystals top 3800m about 1200m fall streaks below, intermittently seeding stratocu 1500m ish. Cloud top T about -12, strong inversion capping the layer.

[11:39] <STFC> Reflectivities up to about +5dBZ in places so probably a reasonable ice water content

[11:39] <STFC> (and almost certainly supercooled water at the top). Some evidence of convective overturning at cloud top from spectral width, typical of supercooled.

[11:39] [FAAM_MSci] Approaching boscombe down for low level approach overshoot now 1140

[11:46] <PaulWilly> have you any low level over passes of Chilbolton planned?

[11:50] [FAAM_MSci] We are profiling up to about 4000m, then working S&L runs through cloud in descending levels.

[11:53] <STFC> We are now scanning along 255 radial - layer seems to be pretty consistent out to at least 60km W of Chilbolton. Seems to be a region of stronger reflectivities out at 15-22km range - maybe more active in this region

[11:54] [FAAM_MSci] PaulWilly: current thoughts are that significant low level cloud along legs will prevent us from coming below 2300ft (min safety alt). probably in cloud at that height.

[11:55] <STFC> Lidar indicates stratcu cloud base about 600m to yeah you'd be in cloud at that height

[11:59] <TomC> Going to see some students, I will stay logged on

[12:01] [FAAM_MSci] 1157L: We are just starting leg ABOVE cloud at FL130 inbound to you. Upper cloud layer tops here @ 11200 ft . Plan thereafter: follow with outbound leg @ FL110 in cloud top, then S&L legs at 1000 ft intervals descending.

[12:03] <STFC> Recent radar scans available as usual www.met.reading.ac.uk/~sws04cdw/realtimeCAMRA.html

[12:04] <STFC> looks like a little shower 18-22km out

[12:07] [FAAM_MSci] Passed the message to M. Sci.

[12:09] [FAAM_MSci] O/H Chilbo @120718 @ FL 130 heading NE.

[12:11] <STFC> does it look like liquid cells at the top?

[12:18] [FAAM_MSci] Getting some good cloud here, although thinning in places along this run. Most cells are mixed phase - predom s/c water, but some ice crystals.

[12:20] [FAAM_MSci] 1219 still on w'ward leg at fl110.

[12:20] <STFC> Great - is that 11kft?

[12:21] [FAAM_MSci] We're working on Flight Levels (Roughly equiv to 000's of feet) - so this run FL110 = approx 11,000ft.

[12:23] <TomC> Very interesting that the radar shows seeding of the Sc by the mid level cloud at times with precip apparently getting to the surface

[12:24] <STFC> Yes, PPI scan suggests patchy light precip, presumably produced by this mechanism. latest RHI shows a patch of high ZDR (oriented planar crystals) very clearly 18-22km range W Chilbolton in top 300m of cloud

[12:27] [FAAM_MSci] Update from 146: end run at FL110 122513; descend to FL100 & return along inbound reciprocal towards Chilbo now (start 1227).

[12:30] <TomC> Cloud structure getting more complex at low levels but main cloud base still at 2 to 2.5 km

[12:32] <STFC> Latest RHI - streak of high ZDR around 20-22km W Chilbolton. Plenty of seeding of low cloud going on out to 25km range.

[12:32] <PaulWilly> Paul signing off.

[12:32] *** PaulWilly (~vircuser@193.63.181.41) has left #APPCLOUDS

[12:42] [FAAM_MSci] O/H Chilbo @FL100 - time 124004 heading ENE.

[12:42] <STFC> any news on what kind of ice you're seeing?

[12:44] [FAAM_MSci] Small needles & large dendrites (few) nowas turning at E end of pattern. Will descend to FL090 for next run outbound, may limit length of run if run out of cloud ...

[12:49] [FAAM_MSci] O/H Chilbo outbound (FL100 desc to FL090): Mixed phase, predom liquid ppn, with v few cloud drops

[12:51] *** Server connection lost

[12:51] *** Server connection lost

[12:51] *** Server connection lost

[12:52] *** Server connection lost

[12:52] *** Server connection lost

[12:53] *** Nickname is already in use: FAAM_MSci

[12:53] *** FAAM146 (~vircuser@203.38.13.2) has joined #APPCLOUDS

[12:53] *** FAAM_MSci (~vircuser@203.52.191.241) has quit IRC [Ping timeout: 240 seconds]

[12:54] <STFC> So is this feature 20km out quite convective then - large supercooled drops & needles? Any Hallett-Mossop?!

[12:57] <TomC> liquid precipitation !

[12:58] [FAAM146] 20km feature: bit bumpy as we traversed, yes. Plenty of water; v. small 'irregulars' - so some Hallett-mossop going on ...

[13:01] <TomC> Interesting that there is no brightband above Chilbolton in the precip

[13:03] <STFC> It's not obvious directly overhead (although you can see a step change in Doppler velocity at 1800m), but if you look at the RHI you can see strong layer of ZDR and some increase in Z associated with melting

[13:04] <TomC> OK then the precip must be ice ?

[13:05] [FAAM146] 146: 130004 start R 5.1 @ FL080, in bound.

[13:05] <TomC> Is it possible we are missing snowfalkes in the online probe data ?

[13:08] <STFC> ZDR signature is amazing, must be loads or oriented crystals in top 600m 20-30km West Chilbolton, and a streak on the edge of the system down to 2200m (FL070)

[13:16] [FAAM146] 131115: passing thro centre of narrow feature - bumpy, with slt turbulence; CPI Pristine cols; much s/c water. some rise in CO2 values.

[13:21] [FAAM146] 1. Missing snowflakes comment ? - we believe we're seeing large dendrites on CPI = pristine snowflakes.

[13:23] [FAAM146] 2. 132145: just passed thro 'convective embedded' feature; some slt turb. At FL070, heading W.

[13:24] [FAAM146] 3. 20km feature (W Chilbo): CVI shows needles & water drops.

[13:31] <TomC> Understood re dendrites I was questioning the liquid precip comment above

[13:35] <TomC> looking on the operational radar precip over Chilbolton quite localised

[13:36] [FAAM146] 133427: starting r 7.1 @6000ft, inbound.

[13:39] <STFC> yes scanning around it appears to be a single band - however it seems pretty much stationary sitting at 20km range for past hour and a half. (the bulk mid-level cloud band seems to be pretty much stationary too looking at IR sat picture). Rainrates at surface likely very low.

[13:40] [FAAM146] Approx: 80 - 90 km W Chilbo into top of (lower) cloudband on this run. Almost exclusively 'water'.

[13:51] <STFC> Is the plan to keep going down into the stratocu to investigate the seeding effect?

[13:52] [FAAM146] o/h chilbo 134835 6000ft, heading ENE.

[13:54] [FAAM146] Interesting 'double feature' of echoes at 20 km w of you. Outer band mainly ice(falling from above); inner band water, LWC = 0.25 g/m3 max.

[13:57] <STFC> maybe liquid water in updraught in the middle, ice spreading out at the top as it glaciates and falling down sides? seems consistent with our ZDR obs

[14:00] <STFC> looking at most recent RHI on aircraft radial, seems to be fizzling out a bit and becoming more layer like - lower Z, ZDR and less ice falling through to lower levels

[14:06] <STFC> Lots of layer ice cloud seeding strato cu overhead at the moment - what level are you flying at now?

[14:18] [FAAM146] OK. Inbound now at 3000ft; next run (lowest) @2300ft likely ...

[14:18] [FAAM146] oops sorry now inbound at 3500 ft ...

[14:19] <STFC> grand - we were just on radio, said you were going to profile up after the FL23 run - sounds good.

[14:30] [FAAM146] Start R 10.1, O/h Chilbo @142916L. 2300ft, heading Westwards..

[14:46] [FAAM146] FYI: On this current run (10.1) at W end have had to depart from usual 255 deg radial to be sig further N (conflicting air traffic).

[14:49] <STFC> no problems we have been scanning slightly north of 255 to get a more general idea of what's going on, so should have some RHIs in that direction too

[14:51] [FAAM146] 144945: Just commencing profile ascent 2300 ft to FL 150 (approx 15000 ft) inbound along radial.

[15:02] [FAAM146] Cloud tops about FL110, so next inbound run will be at FL105. Starting 150139L .

[15:09] <STFC> latest RHI: convective cloud has thinned out a bit at this stage, but still evidence for updraft & liquid at 20km range W chilbolton and high ZDR ice spilling out.

[15:10] [FAAM146] Looks like we will have time for another 3 or 4 runs on radials (after this one) ... do you have any preferences for height for one or more of these runs ???

[15:14] [FAAM146] O/H Chilbo at FL105 @ 151415L.

[15:15] <STFC> There is high ZDR between FL85-105 - maybe FL95?

[15:20] [FAAM146] 151850: start of next run (o/h Chilbo) at FL110 heading W,wards.

[15:27] <STFC> To clarify high ZDR ice is only at 18-25km range; rest of ice at these levels is probably just virga from the more stratiform stuff

[15:27] <STFC> reflectivity is also much lower than the earlier runs, definately weaker feature than before

[15:29] [FAAM146] FYI: next run inbound will be at requested FL095 - visually in relatively cloud free zone, but with falling ppn/crystals from above.

[15:46] <STFC> Did you see any ice?

[15:47] [FAAM146] 1545: just passed o/h chilbo, will descend soon & fly final leg w'bound at 5000ft; with final e'bound leg at 6000 ft before returning to base ...

[15:47] <TomC> still here

[15:51] <STFC> cloud <0C definately much thinner on aircraft radial now - real juicy stuff is West to WNW direction - convective with +30dBZ of reflectivity

[15:51] [FAAM146] O/h Chilbo @154855 descending FL095 to 5000 ft. Snowing O/h Chilbolton at FL095.

[15:55] [FAAM146] 155351: now at 5000ft & heading along radiial W'bound run 14.1, mainly at cloud top so far ...

[15:56] [FAAM146] 155545 descending to keep in cloud tops (to about 4000 ft)

[15:58] [FAAM146] Shame we haven't got another 1-2 hours on task to investigate 'real juicy stuff' - alas we must head home to Cranfield after next run inbound ...

[16:01] <STFC> Yep, can't win em all. Data from the runs earlier on should be very interesting

[16:03] <STFC> LOOKING ALONG 255 RADIAL - SUDDEN PUFF OF CONVECTIVE CLOUD +10dBZ - any chance of going up to investigate for last run?

[16:05] <STFC> Peak Z is approx FL100

[16:07] [FAAM146] Sorry - we're capped at 6000 ft. along this leg ... but we should pass through plume (from what we acn see) at about 20 km range at this height on our fin

Date:18feb09	Operator:KT/JC	DRS Time:set@09:12	DAU1 Time:set	DAU2 Time:set	DAU3 Time:	AUX1 Time:set	Aux2 Time:set
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	PCASP		2DC		2DP		CDP		FFSSP		UMan FSSP		PIP	
Operated?	Y		Y		N		Y		Y		Y		Ydir	
Pre-flight checks	Vref (>7):	4.1	EI#1 V (>1):	-1.9	EI#1V:		Laser V(~3):	4	Ref V (~3):	3.4	Laser V (~9):		EI#1 V:	1.9
	Flow (~1):	0.84	EI#32 V (>1):	-1.6									EI#32V:	3.4
	Pressure:	1014											EI#64 V:	2.3
	Temp (NDIT)	10.3												

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP Blocks Tx	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	Counts	Max size	LWC	
Heaters on after take off 11:10																	
1141	50ft							Water									Boscombe
																	Profile 2.1
1150	4200ft																All water
1154	10000ft							Mixed?									Top of lower layer
1156	12000																In upper layer
																	Cloud tops
1157	f1130	20	0..07	0	0			Clear air	433	0	0	0	0				Start Run 1.1
1203	F1130	20	0.07	0	0			Clear air	433	0	0	0	0				Approaching Chilbolton
1207	F1130	17	0.07	0	0			Clear air clear above	433	0	0	0	0				Chilbolton overhead

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP Blocks Tx	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	Counts	Max size	LWC	
1212																	Descending to fl100
1213	Fl110	2	0.07	2	0			mixed	468	20	10						Start run 2.1
1220	Fl110	3	0.2	1	0			mixed	524								
1222	Fl110	20	0.2	3	0			water	532	400	20			4	100		
1225																	End run 2.1
1226	Fl100	3	0.07	5	0			water	709	0				2	500		Start run 3.1
1229	Fl100							water		30							Isolated Small droplets
1240	Fl100	16	0.07	6	0			mixed	752	0							
1245	Fl090	20	0.07	200				mixed	757								Start run 4.1
1250																	Pip airspeed set to manual 100m/s
1252	Fl090	10	0.06	0	0			mixed	757	0	0			0	0		
1256	Fl090	12	0.06	25				water	758	0	0			0	0		
1258																	End run 4.1
1300	Fl080	18	0.06	0	0				758	0	0			0	0		Start run 5.1
1311	Fl080	16	0.07	109	750			mixed	761	40	15			0.02	6000		20km feature
1319	Fl080																End run 5.1
1320	Fl070	11	0.07	0	0			columns	779	50	10			0.025	5000		Start run 6.1
1332																	End run 6.1
1334	Fl060																Start run 7.1
1347	Fl060	10	0.07	5				Ice columns on 2dc drops on pip	804	40	15			0.001	4000		20km feature large ice & columns then water droplets
1354																	Chilbolton descending

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP Blocks Tx	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	Counts	Max size	LWC	
1356	FI050	17	0.06	8				water	869	0	0			0.000 5	2000		Start run 8.1
1401		40	0.1	81	75			water	924	40	14			0	0		Cloud top penetration
1405								Clear air									
1412								Clear air									End run 8.1
1414	FI035	22	0.2	61	100			water	1006	30	15			0	0		Start run 9.1
1422	FI035	20	0.1	450				water	1228	40	15			0	0		
1426	FI035	30	0.18	150	75			water	1280	60	12			0	0		Overhead chilbolton
1427		200	0.18	447	150			water	1353	40	15			0	0		End run 9.1
1429	FI020	20	0.13	377	250			water	1382	40	15			0	0		Start run 10.1 o/h chilbolton
1434	FI020	80	0.17	328	400			water	1477	60	10			0.005	4000		
1438	FI020	144	0.1	360	250			water	1702	25	20			0.04	5000		
1446	FI020	70	0.08	0	0				1949	0	0			0	0		
1450	FI020	68	0.1	4				water	2067	40	8			0	0		End run 10.1
1502	FI105	5	0.07	0	0			Plates	2178	80	10			0	0		Run 11.1
1514	FI105	10	0.07	7				ice	2183								O/h chilbolton
1518	FI105	1	0.36	10				rosettes	2202	60	10			0.002	1000		End run 11.1
1519	FI110	1	0.1	0	0			mixed	2281	0	0			0	0		Run 12.1
1531	FI110	2	0.23	0	0				2410	0				0			End run 12.1
1533	FI095	15	0.07	0	0				2410	0				0			Run 13.1
1542								Mixed									Short cloud penetration
1544								Clear air									O/h chilbolton
1548								Snow!									End run 13.1
1554	FI050	37	0.07	0				Mixed	2435	0				0			Run 14.1
1556	FI040	40	0.08	0				Clear air	2435	0				0			Run 15.1
1559	FI040	50	0.21	155	75				2453	30	10			0			cloud
1601	FI040																End run 15.1
1603	FI060	12	0.08	0	0			Clear air	2482	0				0			Run 16.1
1613	FI060																End run 16.1

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			Blocks Tx	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	Counts	Max size	

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics		Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP	Vref:	3.87	
	Flow:		
2DC	EI#1:	2.2	
	EI#32:	2	
2DP	EI#1:		Not fitted
FFSSP	Ref V:	3.3	
CDP	Laser V:	3.9	
UMan FSSP	Laser V:	9.5	
PIP	EI#1:	1.6	
	EI#32:	3.1	
	EI#64:	2.5	
Rack Equipment			Please note SEADAS disk space remaining. 1.4G

Flight:

B430

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B430

Date: 18/02/09

Issues

Instruments

Dry Nephelometer data appears ok at Nephelometer rack, but HORACE data does not seem to match that seen at the rack itself.

Wet Nephelometer Log

Flight No **B430**

Date 18 Feb 2009

Operator's name Martin Glew

Page 1 of 2

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
1158	1.1	fl130	10.0	2.1	57	up	38	Run above cloud, close to zero scattering, no chance of w/d ratio
1209	1.1	fl130	9.9	0	90	down	35	
121224								Chiller off for change of height followed by in-cloud run
123045	3.1	fl100	10.3	4.1	58	up	40	in cloud
124435	3.1	fl100	11	12	80			Chiller off
124600	4.1	fl090	10.3	11	80		43	Chiller on, in cloud run
1254			10.2	12	92		39	Tweaked chiller temp down on worries about getting wet neph wet
125814	4.1 end	fl090	10.3	12	90			Chiller off, in cloud run
130004	5.1	fl080	10.3	15	86		39	Chiller on, out of cloud at start of run, still little aerosol and some negative
131856	5.1 end	fl080	10.4	20	90			Chiller off for height change, mainly out of cloud
132023	6.1	fl070	10.4	20	88		39	
133257	6.1 end	fl070	10.3	18	92			Chiller off for height change. Still not enough scattering for W/D ratios.
133427	7.1	fl060	10.4	22	90		37	Chiller on, largely out of cloud - in cloud tops of lower cloud deck
135402	7.1 end	fl060	10.5	25	88			Chiller off for descent
135533	8.1	fl050	10.3	23	85		40	More aerosol but still not enough for W/D ratio
140033			10.1	26	93		35	More aerosol, W/D ratio about 2 but great scatter. In cloud tops
140220								Aerosol concs back to zero
140550	8.1	fl050	10.2	28	88		38	Tweak chiller temp upwards
141211	8.1 end	fl050	10.2	28	93			Chiller off for height change

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B430 Chilbolton Radar images

B430 Chilbolton Radar images

3-GHz radar

Wednesday 18 Feb 2009 13:22:23 RHI 8006/111 Azim 258.0°

B430_RHI_132223.png

3-GHz radar

Wednesday 18 Feb 2009 13:54:02 RHI 8006/121 Azim 255.0°

B430_RHI_135402.png

3-GHz radar

Wednesday 18 Feb 2009 14:06:01 RHI 8006/124 Azim 265.0°

B430_RHI_140601.png

B430 Chilbolton Radar images

3-GHz radar

Wednesday 18 Feb 2009 14:13:08 RHI 8006/127 Azim 250.0°

B430_RHI_141308.png

3-GHz radar

Wednesday 18 Feb 2009 14:23:49 RHI 8006/131 Azim 255.0°

B430_RHI_142349.png

3-GHz radar

Wednesday 18 Feb 2009 14:35:59 RHI 8006/135 Azim 265.0°

B430_RHI_143559.png

B430 Chilbolton Radar images

3-GHz radar

Wednesday 18 Feb 2009 15:24:01 RHI 8006/149 Azim 255.0°

B430_RHI_152401.png

3-GHz radar

Wednesday 18 Feb 2009 15:36:20 RHI 8006/154 Azim 255.0°

B430_RHI_153620.png

3-GHz radar

Wednesday 18 Feb 2009 15:40:33 RHI 8006/156 Azim 255.0°

B430_RHI_154033.png

B430 Chilbolton Radar images

3-GHz radar

Wednesday 18 Feb 2009 15:57:09 RHI 8006/161 Azim 255.0°

B430_RHI_155709.png

B430 Satpics

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 18 Feb 2009 1300 UTC

ukvis_sat_200902181300.jpg

B430 Satpics

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 18 Feb 2009 1400 UTC

ukvis_sat_200902181400.jpg

EIEB51 MSG 108 micron Infrared Image 18 Feb 2009 1400 UTC

ukir_sat_200902181400.jpg

B430 Satpics

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 18 Feb 2009 1500 UTC

ukvis_sat_200902181500.jpg

EIEB51 MSG 108 micron Infrared Image 18 Feb 2009 1500 UTC

ukir_sat_200902181500.jpg

Just arrived FL100 transit

Holes in CT to LHS

P0.1 descending

Turning out of mid cloud

FL60 holding

P0.2 Descending into Boscombe

CB

Main CB

End P0.2 at 50ft P1.1 start

1000ft

Flight B430 11:42:51
Heading 233 deg Speed 207 knots Height 1.5kft Press 959mb
Lat 51°6.0'N Long 1°48.0'W Wind 3 ms-1/ 165 deg
Temp 5.95C Dewpoint 6.73C
From 10:44:22 to now

Current values
GIN LONGITUDE -1.81 deg (+ve E) Draw plane
GIN LATITUDE 51.12 deg (+ve N)

Flight B430 11:43:06
Heading 233 deg Speed 214 knots Height 2.0kft Press 941mb
Lat 51°6.0'N Long 1°48.0'W Wind 2 ms-1/ 157 deg
Temp 5.09C Dewpoint 6.04C
From 10:44:22 to now

Current values
GIN LONGITUDE -1.83 deg (+ve E) Draw plane
GIN LATITUDE 51.12 deg (+ve N)

End P1.1 at FL23 start R0

End R0 start P2.1

P2.1 CT

Turning – still in P2.1

CT P2.1

End P2.1 start R1.1

http://horace:1500/ - Microsoft Internet Explorer

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Back Forward Stop Refresh Home Search Favorites Media Print Mail

Address http://horace:1500/#bottom Go Links

Flight Summary B430

Event	Start	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Stop	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Comment
!	09:43:51	308	-.03kft	52.1N	0.6W						Horace restarted after freeze
!	10:54:48	128	-.04kft	52.1N	0.6W						engine start
T/O	11:07:33	211	0.38kft	52.1N	0.6W						from Cranfield 110708
!	11:09:09	035	3.0kft	52.1N	0.7W						CPC logging started
!	11:15:04	253	10.0kft	52.3N	0.6W						Nev JW zero
!	11:16:00	253	10.0kft	52.3N	0.7W						started WAS sampling sequence
!	11:28:13	171	6.0kft	51.7N	1.6W						JW Nev zero?
!	11:33:46	138	4.3kft	51.4N	1.5W						approach to Bosc start 112420
!	11:40:37	230	0.70kft	51.2N	1.7W						start final approach B Down 113840
!	11:41:44	229	0.12kft	51.2N	1.7W						end approach BD at 50ft
Profile 1.1	11:42:51	233	1.5kft	51.1N	1.8W	11:43:54	251	2.3kft	51.1N	1.9W	from 50ft -5s
Profile 2.1	11:48:09	250	2.3kft	51.0N	2.3W	11:56:59	054	13.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	
!	11:51:32	250	6.1kft	50.9N	2.6W						JW Nev zero
!	11:54:35	092	10.0kft	50.8N	2.8W						Nev JW zero
Run 1.1	11:57:00	054	13.0kft	50.9N	2.6W						

descending into cloud

CT - just after

Start R2.1

Through CB

Well into cloud now

End R2.1 start P3.1

End P3.1 start R3.1

Pristine plates / dendrites

Out of cloud here

Into cloud “feature”

OH CH

Turning

End R3.1 start P4.1

OH CH

End P4.1 start R4.1

Into feature - bumpy - more drops

Out of

End R4.1 start P5.1 out of cloud...

End P5.1 start R5.1 but lots ppt

CPI no ppt here at all 45km out

Centre of feature - bumpy

OH CH

End R5.1 start P6.1

End P6.1 start R6.1 - just into feature/cloud Out of cloud - still bumpy

Small isolated layer cloud

End R6.1 start R7.1

End P7.1 start R7.1

Just into cloud 200-300 below CT

Out of cloud

Start of feature - cloud N and S of us

OH CH

End R7.1 start P8.1

OH CH

End P8.1 start R8.1

Just going into CTs

traffic

Turning at FL50 - traffic

End R8.1 start P9.1

P9.1 FL40

End P9.1 start R9.1

MSci3 lots LW CPI eyeball integration 1g/m3

OH CH

End R9.1 start P10.1

OH CH end P10.1 start R10.1

End R10.1 start P11.1

P11.1 out of CT by some way

FL100 clear air

CT P11.1

P11.1 end start P11.2

End P11.2 start R11.1

Flight B430 15:05:25
Heading 76 deg Speed 234 knots Height 10.5kft Press 682mb
Lat 50°54.0'N Long 2°18.0'W Wind 2 ms-1/0 deg
Temp -11.12C Dewpoint -9.89C
From 14:49:00 to now

Current values
— STATIC PRESSURE 682.66 mb
— DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP -11.12 deg C
— DEW POINT -9.89 deg C

Flight B430 15:05:52
Heading 73 deg Speed 238 knots Height 10.5kft Press 682mb
Lat 50°54.0'N Long 2°18.0'W Wind 2 ms-1/31 deg
Temp -10.97C Dewpoint -10.02C
From 10:44:22 to now

Current values
— GIN LONGITUDE -2.31 deg (+ve E)
— GIN LATITUDE 50.98 deg (+ve N) Draw plane

A/c anti-ice triggered

OH CH

End R11.1 start P12.1

End P12.1 start R12.1

Flight Summary B430

Event	Start	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Stop	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Comment
!	09:43:51	308	-.03kft	52.1N	0.6W						Horace restarted after freeze
!	10:54:48	128	-.04kft	52.1N	0.6W						engine start
T/O	11:07:33	211	0.38kft	52.1N	0.6W						from Cranfield 110708
!	11:09:09	035	3.0kft	52.1N	0.7W						CPC logging started
!	11:15:04	253	10.0kft	52.3N	0.6W						Nev JW zero
!	11:16:00	253	10.0kft	52.3N	0.7W						started WAS sampling sequence
!	11:28:13	171	6.0kft	51.7N	1.6W						JW Nev zero?
!	11:33:46	138	4.3kft	51.4N	1.5W						approach to Bosc start 112420
!	11:40:37	230	0.70kft	51.2N	1.7W						start final approach B Down 113840
!	11:41:44	229	0.12kft	51.2N	1.7W						end approach BD at 50ft
Profile 1.1	11:42:51	233	1.5kft	51.1N	1.8W	11:43:54	251	2.3kft	51.1N	1.9W	from 50ft -5s
Profile 2.1	11:48:09	250	2.3kft	51.0N	2.3W	11:56:59	054	13.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	
!	11:51:32	250	6.1kft	50.9N	2.6W						JW Nev zero
!	11:54:35	092	10.0kft	50.8N	2.8W						Nev JW zero
Run 1.1	11:57:00	054	13.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	12:12:27	256	12.7kft	51.1N	1.5W	
!	11:58:15	071	13.0kft	51.0N	2.4W						Nev JW zero
!	12:07:30	062	13.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						overhead Chilbolton
!	12:08:49	059	13.0kft	51.2N	1.3W						Nev JW zero
Run 2.1	12:13:52	257	11.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	12:25:12	249	11.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	
!	12:24:05	253	11.0kft	50.9N	2.7W						in icing, turb probe so far ok
Profile 3.1	12:25:26	224	10.9kft	50.9N	2.8W	12:26:17	125	10.1kft	50.8N	2.8W	
Run 2.1	12:26:59	040	10.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	12:44:25	257	10.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	start profile

Profile 3.1	12:25:26	224	10.9kft	50.9N	2.8W	12:26:17	125	10.1kft	50.8N	2.8W	
Run 3.1	12:26:58	040	10.0kft	50.8N	2.7W	12:44:35	257	10.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	at end profile
!	12:36:29	078	10.0kft	51.1N	1.8W						JW Nev zero
!	12:40:05	061	10.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						overhead Chilbolton
Profile 4.1	12:44:35	257	10.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	12:45:55	256	9.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	
!	12:44:57	251	9.8kft	51.1N	1.4W						oh Chil
Run 4.1	12:45:55	256	9.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	12:58:13	253	9.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Profile 5.1	12:58:14	253	9.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	13:00:03	047	8.0kft	50.8N	2.8W	
Run 5.1	13:00:04	047	8.0kft	50.8N	2.8W	13:18:55	247	8.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	
!	13:09:52	072	8.0kft	51.1N	1.8W						Nev JW zero
!	13:13:52	071	8.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						o/h Chil
Profile 6.1	13:18:56	247	8.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	13:20:22	259	7.1kft	51.1N	1.6W	
Run 6.1	13:20:23	259	7.1kft	51.1N	1.6W	13:32:57	256	7.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Profile 7.1	13:32:57	256	7.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	13:34:26	080	6.1kft	50.8N	2.8W	
Run 7.1	13:34:27	073	6.0kft	50.8N	2.8W	13:54:02	259	6.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	
!	13:40:38	072	6.0kft	51.0N	2.2W						JW Nev zero
!	13:42:43	072	6.0kft	51.0N	2.1W						Heimann Cal
!	13:49:20	059	6.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						o/h Chil
Profile 8.1	13:54:02	259	6.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	13:55:32	258	5.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	
!	13:54:27	250	5.8kft	51.1N	1.4W						oh Chil
Run 8.1	13:55:33	259	5.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	14:12:10	055	5.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	
!	14:07:29	254	5.0kft	50.9N	2.6W						JW Nev zero
Profile 9.1	14:12:11	055	5.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	14:14:33	071	3.5kft	51.0N	2.4W	
Run 9.1	14:14:33	071	3.5kft	51.0N	2.4W	14:27:23	099	3.5kft	51.2N	1.4W	
!	14:25:45	019	3.5kft	51.1N	1.4W						oh Chil
Profile 10.1	14:27:24	106	3.5kft	51.2N	1.4W	14:29:15	256	2.1kft	51.1N	1.4W	

Profile 7.1	13:32:57	256	7.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	13:34:26	080	6.1kft	50.8N	2.8W	
Run 7.1	13:34:27	073	6.0kft	50.8N	2.8W	13:54:02	259	6.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	
!	13:40:38	072	6.0kft	51.0N	2.2W						JW Nev zero
!	13:42:43	072	6.0kft	51.0N	2.1W						Heimann Cal
!	13:49:20	059	6.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						o/h Chil
Profile 8.1	13:54:02	259	6.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	13:55:32	258	5.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	
!	13:54:27	250	5.8kft	51.1N	1.4W						oh Chil
Run 8.1	13:55:33	259	5.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	14:12:10	055	5.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	
!	14:07:29	254	5.0kft	50.9N	2.6W						JW Nev zero
Profile 9.1	14:12:11	055	5.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	14:14:33	071	3.5kft	51.0N	2.4W	
Run 9.1	14:14:33	071	3.5kft	51.0N	2.4W	14:27:23	099	3.5kft	51.2N	1.4W	
!	14:25:45	019	3.5kft	51.1N	1.4W						oh Chil
Profile 10.1	14:27:24	106	3.5kft	51.2N	1.4W	14:29:15	256	2.1kft	51.1N	1.4W	
Run 10.1	14:29:16	256	2.1kft	51.1N	1.4W	14:49:45	175	2.1kft	50.9N	2.8W	
!	14:29:58	256	2.1kft	51.1N	1.5W						oh Chil at start run 10.1
Profile 11.1	14:49:45	175	2.1kft	50.9N	2.8W	14:59:03	243	12.7kft	50.9N	2.8W	
!	14:54:36	053	8.1kft	51.0N	2.4W						Nev JW zero
!	14:55:28	303	8.9kft	51.0N	2.4W						Heimann cal
Profile 11.2	14:59:04	243	12.7kft	50.9N	2.8W	15:01:39	058	10.6kft	50.9N	2.7W	
Run 11.1	15:01:39	058	10.6kft	50.9N	2.7W	15:18:25	285	10.5kft	51.1N	1.4W	
!	15:07:31	074	10.5kft	51.0N	2.1W						Nev JW zero
!	15:14:16	073	10.5kft	51.1N	1.4W						o/h Chil
Profile 12.1	15:18:26	285	10.5kft	51.1N	1.4W	15:18:57	261	11.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	chl
Run 12.1	15:19:13	262	11.0kft	51.1N	1.5W						

End R12.1 just above CT start P13.1

End P13.1 start R13.1

Into thin cloud - more ahead

Thick cloud feature - short pass

OH CH

Right turn PEPIS

End R13.1 start P14.1

OH CH

End P14.1 start R14.1 just into CT

End R14.1 start P15.1

End P15.1 start R15.1 still^CT

Cloud

End R15.1 start P16.1

CT

End P16.1 start R16.1

End R16.1 start P17.1

OH CH

End P17.1

